
INAIL Case Study on the Non-Traditional Rehabilitation of Rainwater Pipes in a Large Historic Office Building

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Table of contents

Abstract	1
Keywords	2
Terms, definitions and acronyms	2
Introduction and background	2
Grey cast iron downpipes, advantages and issues	5
Grey cast iron, most likely causes of failure	7
Rehabilitation technique adopted	8
Work equipment	9
Work phases	9
Conclusions	10
Author biographies	12
Declaration of Competing Interest	12
Acknowledgement	12
Normative references	12
References	12

Abstract

All historic buildings constructed in the first half of the last century made extensive use of grey cast iron rainwater pipes, which, as is well known, is a fragile material prone to corrosion. In addition to the inherent weaknesses of the material, rainwater pipes are continuously subjected to environmental stresses (stray currents, temperatures, vibrations, freeze-thaw cycles, and ageing of seals), which, in large city centres like Milan, are not negligible.

Rainwater pipes in operation for over sixty years develop failures that lead to the gradual deterioration of the building's structures, and the damage can be quite significant when it comes to pipes buried within masonry.

This is the case of the rainwater pipes considered in this study, which are embedded in the external walls of the INAIL headquarters building in Milan city center.

The building is used as offices and is located in a high pedestrian traffic area; therefore, the several constraints imposed by the owner were quite stringent as well. The traditional method of replacement, demolition, and subsequent reinstatement of the rainwater drainage system on the roof could not be used. Engineers were required to design an *in-situ* rehabilitation system to meet the mandatory requirements for repairing the rainwaters.

An internal pipe lining system was used, which provided significant advantages in terms of health and safety at work, design, project management, speed of execution, as well as minimal environmental impact both inside and outside the building. This study details:

- the phenomenon of failures in grey cast iron rainwater pipes;
- the lining technology using resin polymerisation;
- the phases of the work carried out in compliance with the current UNI 13566-1 and 4 standard and
- the final conclusions.

Keywords: Pipe Maintenance, No-Dig Technology, CIPP, Cure In Place Pipe, Rainwater Leakage, Downpipe, Relining, Pipe Rehabilitation.

Terms, definitions and acronyms

Curing: Process of resin polymerisation by the use of heat or exposure to light.

Composite: Composition of elements in sheets or membranes assembled to provide the required requirements.

Lining tube: A flexible tube, consisting of a liner which carries the liquid resin during insertion into the pipe, membranes to create a structural thickness.

Replacement: Rehabilitation of an existing piping system by installing a new piping system, without incorporating original artifacts

Rehabilitation: All measures to restore or improve the performance of an existing pipeline

Internal membrane: Membrane which forms the inside surface of the pipe after installation.

Eversion method: the process of turning a flexible tube inside out using water or air pressure.

Pot life: A chemical reaction index that indicates the time within which the resin can be applied before the polymerisation process and the resulting increase in viscosity begin, making the resin no longer workable

CIPP: Technology to provide a cured in place pipe.

Introduction and background

The building owned by INAIL, is located on Via Mazzini, just a few steps from cathedral square. It was designed in the late 1940s and is used as office space. The building consists of 8 floors above ground and 2 underground floors, with a gross area of 1,700 m² per floor.

The roof rainwater drainage system is made up of several rainwater pipes embedded in the walls. The pipes are made of grey cast iron, and during heavy rainfall, water also leaked outside the pipes, wetting the wall from the inside and causing large and visible stains on the office walls.

The water leakage was due to:

1. Unsealed spigot joints;
2. Holes in the pipes made by the air conditioning installer to discharge condensation water;
3. Natural corrosion holes.

The traditional replacement method would require the demolition of part of the internal wall, causing significant disruption to both INAIL employees and INAIL visitors. On the contrary, performing the work from the public street is not feasible because:

- The works would have a significant impact on pedestrian traffic.
- There are operational challenges due to the complex façade.
- Both the municipality and the heritage authority overseeing historic buildings would be involved.

For these key reasons, the non-destructive Cured In Place Pipe (CIPP) technique was employed to relining 100 mm diameter rainwater pipes.

This technique allows the *in-situ* repair or full rehabilitation of a pipe by internally lining it with a pipe created through the polymerisation of thermosetting resins.

Before discussing the CIPP technology and installation procedures, information on grey cast iron rainwater pipes and the failure mechanism of cast iron pipes is provided below.

rainwater pipe embedded in the wall

View of the first façade (Via Giardino, Milan)

rainwater pipe embedded in the wall

View of the first and second façade

View of the second façade (Via Mazzini, Milan)

rainwater pipe embedded in the wall

View of the second and third façade

Grey cast iron downpipes, advantages and issues

This type of cast iron was widely used due to its properties and the manufacturing techniques of the time.

In the early decades of the 1900s, drainpipes were made of gray cast iron, as ductile cast iron was patented in 1940 and its first applications began from 1950 onwards.

Grey cast iron has been widely used due to its resistance to corrosion from both the fluid and the external environment. Until the 1950s, it was the only type of cast iron employed, and it was produced by melting blast furnace cast iron and cast-iron scrap (ordinary second-melting cast iron), featuring a lamellar arrangement of graphite crystals (see following figure)

Graphite flakes in
grey cast iron

Micrograph of grey cast iron

It is the most brittle material, and its tensile strength, a value of particular relevance for pressure pipes, ranges from 150 to 350 N/mm². But this is not our case, as in this discussion, we are examining small-diameter, non-pressurised drainage pipes.

The grey cast iron used for rainwater pipes has a cemented iron matrix. This matrix is typically composed of a combination of ferrite and cementite (iron carbide). The presence of graphite flakes in the matrix contributes to the grey cast iron's characteristics of strength, ductility, and workability, making it suitable for use in applications such as rainwater pipes. The distribution of graphite and the composition of the matrix also influence the mechanical properties of the material.

Mechanical fracture is a phenomenon that leads to damage of components even under low stress conditions. At a macroscopic level, it consists of the disintegration of the material into smaller fragments due to the breaking of the chemical bonds that hold the atoms together. These bonds are broken by excessive energy concentration through processes that depend on numerous external and internal factors related to the material.

The fracture mechanism is that of classic brittle fracture characterized by low stress. In brittle fracture, the material subjected to stress does not undergo (at least macroscopically) plastic deformation, and the break occurs within the elastic range.

From a microscopic perspective, the fracture propagates along the grain boundaries (metal crystals) that make up the fractured material (intergranular fracture) or through a fracture within the grains themselves (transgranular fracture).

All of this makes fracture a rather complex phenomenon to predict, especially in the case of alloys with complex microstructures.

Fractured surface of grey cast iron

Despite the limitations of this metallic piping, its widespread use in the past has resulted in this type of pipe constituting a large portion of the downpipes in many buildings because of the following reasons:

- **Cost-effective:** Gray cast iron was relatively inexpensive to produce and was readily available.
- **Corrosion resistance:** While not as corrosion-resistant as modern materials, gray cast iron still offered sufficient durability to withstand exposure to moisture and the elements, which was crucial for drainpipes.
- **Strength and rigidity:** The material's mechanical strength made it well-suited for structural applications like drainpipes, which needed to handle the weight of water and resist environmental stresses.
- **Ease of casting:** Gray cast iron is easy to cast and shape, which allowed manufacturers to produce pipes with standardized dimensions and even some decorative elements for architectural purposes.
- **Aesthetic and function:** In addition to their practical function, cast iron downpipes often had a decorative appearance, complementing the aesthetic of the buildings of that era.
- **Ease of installation:** This joint design allows for relatively easy alignment and assembly of pipes, especially in systems where straight runs of piping are required.

Now we list the cases of downpipe failures

Corrosion: Although cast iron is durable, over time, exposure to moisture, atmospheric agents, and rainwater can cause rust and corrosion, especially in the presence of acidic or contaminated water.

Cracking: Cast iron downpipes may develop cracks or fissures due to the constant thermal expansion and contraction, particularly in climates with significant temperature fluctuations between hot and cold.

Accumulation of debris: Leaves, branches, and other debris can accumulate inside the downpipe, causing blockages. If water cannot drain properly, the pressure can damage the structure.

Wear over time: Like all materials, cast iron has a limited lifespan. After decades of use, downpipes can weaken and lose some of their strength.

Structural movement: Buildings, especially older ones, may experience movement or settlement. This can create stress on the downpipes, leading to cracks or breaks.

Manufacturing defects: Imperfections in the cast iron, such as inclusions or porosity, can make the downpipe more vulnerable to cracking.

The combination of these factors can reduce the functionality and lifespan of cast iron downpipes, requiring maintenance or replacement.

Grey cast iron, most likely causes of failure

Disregarding the various possible causes of failure, we will focus on those that seem most likely after reviewing the video inspection. The causes considered are:

- Thermal stress (with particular attention to freeze-thaw cycles);
- Corrosion of metal pipes;
- Poor functioning of the bell-and-spigot joint
- Vibrations.

The variation in temperature causes a proportional change in the linear dimensions of the pipe. The problem becomes more significant the more the pipeline is constrained. Conversely, the presence of bell-and-spigot joints significantly reduces the stresses in the material.

Freeze and thaw cycles influence cracks making the material brittle

Cast iron is susceptible to electrolytic corrosion even though it is less prone to corrosion compared to mild steel because it contains more cementite (Fe_3C), a structure composed of iron and carbon that is more resistant to corrosion than ferrite or pearlite.

In the case of cast iron, oxides, hydroxides, and salts formed from the corrosion of ferrite remain in place along with graphite (graphitization). A corroded pipe may appear intact and may not show any signs of leakage. Only a dull sound upon percussion and its ease of scratching reveal its true condition. Prolonged or sudden stresses (vibrations) can compromise it suddenly.

Rehabilitation technique adopted

No-dig technologies are varied and applied depending on the specific case configuration. The issue presented here involves pipes that are not buried but embedded in the external wall, for which a non-structural but functional rehabilitation is required.

In this context, rehabilitation refers to:

- Impermeability
- smooth internal surface for flow and
- chemical resistance.

Although video inspection identified specific points of failure, a localised intervention could have been carried out. However, for technical-economic reasons and due to the age of the entire system, it was decided to proceed with the rehabilitation of the entire single pipe.

Nowadays, there are non-destructive technologies for localised repair that offer preferable advantages compared to the replacement of single piece damaged of a rainwater pipe.

The basic principle of repair is simple: inserting an internal pipe into the host pipe and bonding it to the internal wall.

In practical terms, the process is not simple and requires specialised machinery, knowledge of material technology and composite materials, as well as skill in practical application.

After performing the diagnosis of the entire rainwater drainage system and identifying the map of faults, considering the constraints set by the client-owner, it was decided to opt for an *in-situ* reconstruction of the pipe.

Adhering and non-adhering pipe methods were ruled out as it was determined, during the design phase, that reconstructing a new system would be more appropriate.

Among the *in-situ* pipe reconstruction methods, the following were excluded:

- Spiral-wound lining
- Coating
- Cement lining

so that, the preferred method was *in-situ* polymerised lining (CIPP)

CIPP method consists of an impregnated lining tube introduced by eversion in a host pipe to achieve simultaneous both insertion and inflation.

CIPP techniques differ in terms of:

- the method of liner insertion
- the inflation of the liner
- the resin curing technique.

In our case, the resin was cured using UV radiation emitting lamps

Work equipment

The equipment brought by the company entrusted with the work are:

- A. Device for cleaning metal pipes.
- B. Roller device for applying resin.
- C. Inversion drum
- D. Equipment for maintaining and monitoring pressure;
- E. UV light sources for cure epoxy resin;
- F. Finishing equipment such as a robotic cutter for opening lateral connection.

Before applying the lining, it is essential to prepare the surface with mechanical cleaning. Depending on the situation, brushes and/or chains may be suitable. The use of high-pressure water (canal jet) is not always recommended for corroded pipes or those with adhered limescale.

The UV light resin curing device can be automated to maintain a constant speed, which ranges from a few meters per hour, e.g., 10 m/h for DN 300 up to 110 m/h for DN 70. To reduce the required electrical power, while maintaining the same emission level, the lamps are of the LED type. The device can be equipped with a camera and a lubrication system.

Work phases

Preliminary and preparatory operations for rehabilitation intervention. Before proceeding with the actual rehabilitation, the downpipe embedded in the wall was prepared with the following steps:

1. Taking the pipe out of service
2. Preliminary video inspection
3. Mechanical cleaning of the downpipe
4. In-situ liner impregnation
5. Lining tube insertion
6. Cured with UV Lamp
7. Preparation of any lateral connections, if present

The drainage system was deactivated by disconnecting the pipe from the leaf guard on the roof to the horizontal manifold in the basement. It was confirmed that there were no lateral connections along the route.

Leaf guard for the rainwater pipe on the building's roof

The preliminary video inspection, different from the diagnostic inspection, aimed to identify any obstacles that could hinder the proper insertion of the liner inside the pipe, and to detect any lateral connections. During the video inspection, an improper connection of the air conditioning system's condensate drainpipe in the office area was identified.

Delamination of the internal surface
with thinning of the pipe wall

Inner surface of the downpipe
after relining

A thorough cleaning of the downpipe was performed by heavy metal brushes to remove debris, including those adhered to the internal surface.

Before being impregnated with resin, the liner must be vacuumed using vacuum pumps to allow the resin to adequately penetrate the liner. This operation can be done *in situ* when using small-diameter pipes and epoxy resins; otherwise, the process is carried out in a factory using machinery.

Impregnation phase.
Laying of the pipe

Insertion of the resin-catalyst
mixture inside the relining tube

Use of the pinch roller for
distributing the mixture in the felt

Resins naturally harden with temperature, so a catalyst is introduced into the flexible tube to increase the pot-life. For thermosetting resins, the impregnated liner can be stored in a refrigerator and used within 3-4 days. In contrast, when using UV-curing resins, they must be stored in sealed, light-proof containers.

The pre-processed liner thus has the internal support (polyester felt) impregnated with resin. The inversion machine's task is to turn the tube inside out so that the resin-coated side adheres to the internal surface of the pipe to be repaired.

The installer has ensured that the pressure in the lining tube, during eversion or inflation is sufficient to hold it tight to the pipe wall and prevent any internal deformation of the lining tube. The constant pressure for the tube everted was achieved by a low-power air compressor.

In order to a photo cure of the resin the installer has adopted a ultra-violet lamp reducing significantly the curing time of applied resins. The use of a lamp that provides a certain emission, the right power and an adequate speed of the lamp shooting inside the tube allow to control the hardening process and guarantee a uniform hardening time.

Insertion of the liner into the rainwater pipe from the roof

Cured liner from the host pipe in the basement

Removal by cutting of the excess liner

In the rehabilitation of sewage pipes, a pre-liner is sometimes used to prevent resin contamination by water, as some resins do not cure when in contact with water.

When a heat system is used to cure the resin, the temperature must be carefully monitored. Additionally, parameters such as pressure, temperature, speed, must be controlled throughout the process at intervals of sufficient frequency. In the case of hardening with steam, it is recommended to start with low temperatures, e.g. 60°, and increase by 10 degrees every 5 minutes.

At the end of the curing process, the liner must be trimmed at the end, and the downpipe must be connected to the horizontal drain in the basement (see figure). A final inspection and testing shall be executed.

Conclusions

As discussed in this paper, a rainwater drainage system requires maintenance after more than 60 years of operation, such as the one presented here, carrying out maintenance by fully replacing the system embedded in the walls is unfeasible.

It is possible to consider constructing an external system, but this is not always easy or permitted by the authorities overseeing historic buildings.

In these pages, the choice of the rehabilitation system for the drainage system was deliberately based on technical and installation considerations, leaving aside the economic aspect.

However, the same conclusion could have been reached by considering only the economic factor, as it has been demonstrated that the total costs are significantly lower than those of a traditional intervention.

Author biographies

Giacomino Argento is a civil hydraulic engineer specializing in large office building systems maintenance. In the past, he served in construction procedures for the European Commission. In INAIL he has developed detailed designs for a wide range of installations. As a qualified project manager, he oversees public works tenders and bids. His research interests focus on the maintenance of hydraulic systems using non-destructive technologies.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declares that he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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